

SUSTAINABLE TOURISM PRACTICES AND THEIR IMPACT ON TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN BAYAWAN CITY

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ABSTRACT

Sustainable tourism is a vital tool to sustain eco-friendly and socio-economically inclusive development. The growth of tourism in the Philippines is opening up new economic opportunities and sources of livelihood; however, it also poses challenges to the environment and cultural identity. This research aimed to assess the local population's perception of the three components of sustainable tourism practices implemented Bayawan City, Negros Oriental: the zero plastic policy, sustainable utility systems, and cultural heritage preservations. Using a descriptive-correlational research design, the study utilized a purposive sampling to select 240 respondents, composed of local residents, barangay officials, and tourism stakeholders. A validated questionnaire served as the primary instrument for data collection, and the data were analyzed using weighted mean and Pearson correlation coefficient. Findings revealed that sustainable tourism practices significantly impact tourism development, particularly in environmental conservation, economic growth, and community identity. However, results showed no significant relationship between cultural heritage preservation and economic growth. Based on the findings, the study recommended that sustainable tourism practices be integrated into tourism marketing strategies and policy development. These efforts should aim to promote responsible tourism, particularly in emerging rural areas such as Bayawan City.

Keywords: *Sustainable Tourism, Zero Plastic Policy, Cultural Heritage Preservation, Sustainable Utility Systems, Environmental Conservation, Economic Development*

INTRODUCTION

Sustainable tourism as a strategy in tourism development plays a crucial role in environmental protection, providing continued stimulation for the economy, and preserving culture (Thi et al., 2024). However, its full potential is often undermined by challenges such as inconsistent application of sustainable principles, overdevelopment, and limited community participation, which are a constant cause of the problem in the tourism industry (Kilipiris, 2005). Research has shown that wrong planning in tourism can lead to environmental degradation, loss of culture, and inequalities in the socio-economic (Sousa, 2018). These concerns point out the need for securing normal and strategic tourism practices that not only conserve resources but also improve visitors' overall experiences.

In the Philippines, the growth of online tourism has led to the country's economic gains (Dizon et al., 2024). However, these gains could come with potential environmental issues (Abari & Malibiran, 2024). In response, the government has implemented several measures to promote sustainable tourism. The Zero Plastic Policy of Bayawan City, along with the promotion of sustainable utility systems, are among the initiatives by the local government that closely follow the Republic Act No. 9003, known as Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 (Republic of the Philippines, 2001). In the same way, the local authorities and community members have initiated various sustainable-driven programs such as workshop-based programs aimed at preventing coastal erosion, environmental awareness campaigns, and agricultural revitalization projects that support local livelihoods. Furthermore, the Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) issued Memorandum Circular No. 2023-133 of 2023, mandating all barangays to conduct weekly clean-up drives along with the "Barangay at Kalinisan Day (BarKaDa)" initiative, an effort to foster environmental consciousness and community involvement at the local level.

While it is true that the government is actively working on fostering and promoting sustainable tourism in the country, particularly in response to the continuous influx of tourists (Abari & Malibiran, 2024), it is imperative to assess whether existing programs and policies are effectively implemented and communicated among stakeholders. Although existing studies have extensively explored sustainable tourism in urbanized and highly developed tourist destinations (Moscardo, 2014; Zamfir & Corbos, 2015), smaller cities and rural communities such as Bayawan City remain underrepresented in empirical research. This gap in the literature underscores the relevance and necessity of the present study.

This study aimed to evaluate the impact of sustainable tourism practices on tourism development in local communities, with a particular focus on Bayawan City, Negros

Oriental. By analyzing the implementation and effects of initiatives such as zero plastic policy, sustainable utility systems, and cultural heritage preservation, this research sought to provide valuable insights for policymakers, tourism planners, and community leaders. The findings aimed to contribute to crafting more effective, inclusive, and sustainable tourism strategies that not only protect the environment but also support economic vitality and preserve local identity.

Research Questions

The study aimed to investigate the sustainable tourism practices and its impact on tourism development in Bayawan City. It specifically endeavored to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent do the local government and community implement the following sustainable tourism practices:
 - 1.1 Zero plastic policy;
 - 1.2 Integration of Sustainable Utility Systems; and
 - 1.3 Cultural Heritage and Preservation?
2. What is the perceived impact of sustainable tourism practices on tourism development in Bayawan City in terms of the following aspects:
 - 2.1 Environmental Conservation;
 - 2.2 Economic Growth; and
 - 2.3 Community Identity?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent to which the local government and community implement sustainable tourism practices and its perceived impacts on their tourism development?

METHODOLOGY

Data and Respondents

The respondents in this study included local communities, barangay officials, tourism officers, and personnel from the City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office of Bayawan City. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants, given the limited number of target government employees and the large population of residents with direct connections or relevant experience related to the study. This non-probability sampling method allows the researchers to deliberately select respondents who are most knowledgeable and involved in tourism-related planning, policy-making, and implementation.

In gathering the data, the researcher utilized a researcher-made questionnaire based on the researcher's readings from different scholarly articles related to the study. The items were reviewed and validated by the three experts: one holding a Ph.D., another a Master's degree, and one a licensed teacher.

To ensure item reliability, a dry run was conducted on the 30 government employees and residents in the abovementioned cities. The items were tested for their reliability using Cronbach's alpha test.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

The researcher utilized the following tools in analyzing and interpreting the study's data:

Weighted Mean. This was used in getting (a) the extent implementation of sustainable tourism practices (b) the perceived impacts on tourism development.

Pearson correlation coefficient. This was utilized to identify the degree of relationship between the extent implementation of sustainable tourism practices and the perceived impact on tourism development of Bayawan City.

Measures

Dependent variable. The dependent variable considers perceived impacts on tourism development in terms of environmental conservation, economic growth, and community identity in Bayawan City. It was measured using the weighted mean with the following options: always (5 scores), often (4 scores), sometimes (3 scores), seldom (2 scores), and never (1 score).

Independent variable. The independent variable of this study is the sustainable tourism practices, specifically: zero plastic policy, integration of sustainable utility system, and cultural heritage and preservation. These variables are assumed to influence the dependent variable, which is the perceived impacts on tourism development in terms of environmental conservation, economic growth, and community identity in Bayawan City.

RESULTS

Table 1.1
Extent implementation of zero-plastic policy by the local government and community

Zero-Plastic Policy	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. Implements strict rules of waste collection management for residents.	4.72	Always
2. Implements strict rules of waste sorting management for residents.	4.64	Always
3. Implements strict rules of waste recycling management for residents.	4.46	Always
4. Implements alternative materials such as paper bags, paper straws, and eco-bags that could replace single-use plastics.	4.53	Always
5. Implements strict rules and regulations of zero-plastic management in all establishments.	3.51	Often
Composite	4.37	Always

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Always
3.41 – 4.20	Often
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes

1.0 – 2.60 Seldom
 1.00 – 1.80 Never

The data in Table 1.1 reveals that the implementation of the zero-plastic policy is perceived to have “Always” implemented by the local government and community, with an overall composite mean of 4.37. As shown on the table, item 1 garnered the highest rating, with a composite mean of 4.72, which indicates that residents in Bayawan City responsibly adhere to established rules of waste collection management for residents. On the other hand, item 5 garnered a lower composite mean of 3.51, which suggests that implementation of rules and regulations of zero-plastic management are not entirely adhered in all establishments in Bayawan City.

Table 1.2
Extent implementation of the integration of sustainable utility system by the local government and community

Integration of Sustainable Utility System	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. Utilizes wetlands for wastewater treatment for an innovative and sustainable approach to sanitation.	4.48	Always
2. Utilizes biodegradable waste through composting to produce beneficial products like fertilizers.	4.47	Always
3. Utilizes well-managed sanitary landfill.	4.49	Always
4. Educates tourists on sustainable practices through informative signage and digital billboards, encouraging them to minimize their environmental impact.	4.44	Always
5. Utilizes renewal energy sources to reduce carbon footprints.	4.27	Always
Composite	4.43	Always

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Always
3.41 – 4.20	Often
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes
1.81 – 2.60	Seldom
1.00 – 1.80	Never

Table 1.2 presents data on the extent to which the local government and community implement the integration of a sustainable utility system in Bayawan City. The findings reveal an overall composite mean of 4.43, interpreted as "Always," indicating that sustainable utility practices are perceived to have been consistently implemented across sectors of the city.

Table 1.3
Extent implementation of the cultural heritage and preservation by the local government and community

Cultural Heritage and Preservation	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. Celebrates preservation activities for intangible cultural heritage like the Tawo-tawo festival.	4.32	Always
2. Practices character first “Bayawanihan” to emphasize the importance of good character and values in building a strong and sustainable community.	4.01	Often

3. Showcases hands-on activities, workshops, and demonstrations that help sustain tourism development.	3.99	Often
4. Educates the local community about the importance of cultural heritage like raising awareness and responsible behavior through seminars.	3.95	Often
5. Communicates with local communities to sustain its authentic host culture.	4.01	Often
Composite	4.06	Often
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	
4.21 – 5.00	Always	
3.41 – 4.20	Often	
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes	
1.81 – 2.60	Seldom	
1.00 – 1.80	Never	

Table 1.3 reveals that the cultural heritage and preservation are “Often” implemented in Bayawan City, with an overall composite mean of 4.06. This shows that among the cultural preservation initiatives, celebrating Tawo-tawo festival has deeply woven into the lives of Bayawanons, with a weighted mean of 4.32, correlating to “Always”. It highlights that the spirit of this festival is still present and highly appreciated by Bayawanons, who are actively involved in preserving this intangible cultural heritage.

Table 2.1
Perceived impact of sustainable tourism practices on tourism development in Bayawan City in terms of environmental conservation

Environmental Conservation	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. Support coastal management programs like clean up drives.	4.55	Always
2. Encourage sustainable agricultural initiatives such as giving free seedlings to the local farmers and promoting training programs.	4.41	Always
3. Promote community participation in environmental conservation such as conducting seminars and tree planting.	4.44	Always
4. Shifting toward cleaner transportation such as “potpot” or electric tricycles.	4.52	Always
5. Strengthen policies for environmental conservation to protect biodiversity within the reserve area.	4.44	Always
Composite	4.47	Always
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	
4.21 – 5.00	Always	
3.41 – 4.20	Often	
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes	
1.81 – 2.60	Seldom	
1.00 – 1.80	Never	

Table 2.1 reveals that the perceived impact of sustainable tourism practices on tourism development in terms of environmental conservation is “Always”, with an overall composite mean of 4.47. This implies that the community greatly supports environmental efforts, particularly in coastal clean-up campaigns, which received a weighted mean of 4.55 “Always”.

Table 2.2**Perceived impact of sustainable tourism practices on tourism development in Bayawan City in terms of economic growth**

Economic Growth	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. Support local businesses by buying local products and recommending them to other people.	4.47	Always
2. Invest in Agricultural development like providing seedlings to advance agri-industrial development	4.36	Always
3. Provides investment in the development of plantation and diversified crops including rubber trees, banana, cassava, coffee, cacao, and vegetables.	4.38	Always
4. Utilize agri-farming and aquaculture programs like Danapa Inland Aquaculture Program which supports farmers through the Department of Agriculture who market their products directly in the city.	4.36	Always
5. Emerge new industries such as Hass Avocado Development to significantly impact the local economy.	3.83	Often
Composite	4.28	Always

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Always
3.41 – 4.20	Often
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes
1.81 – 2.60	Seldom
1.00 – 1.80	Never

Table 2.2 reveals that the perceived impact of sustainable tourism practices on economic growth is “Always,” with an overall composite mean of 4.28. Survey participants agreed that sustainable tourism is a leading economic development force. Notably, strengthening local businesses through local purchasing and recommendations, with composite mean of 4.47 as “Always”, demonstrates how community support serves as vital economic sustainability element. On the other hand, item 3 garnered a slightly low composite mean of 3.83 as “Often.” It can be inferred that the government and residents’ initiative in the hass-avocado industry may not have that widely known in the city.

Table 2.3**Perceived impact of sustainable tourism practices on tourism development in Bayawan City in terms of community identity**

Community Identity	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description
1. Strengthen the character first of Bayawanons as a sense of identity.	4.45	Always
2. Encourage community participation in activities that promote character development through festivals and celebrations like Tawo-tawo Festival and Charter Anniversary.	4.34	Always
3. Promote inclusivity for a better community.	4.35	Always
4. Practice a holistic approach to community building which can contribute to a more prosperous society by preserving historical sites and cultures.	4.41	Always

5. Utilize programs and activities for the local community such as educational programs and volunteer opportunities.	4.43	Always
Composite	4.40	Always

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description
	4.21 – 5.00	Always
	3.41 – 4.20	Often
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes
	1.81 – 2.60	Seldom
	1.00 – 1.80	Never

Table 2.3 shows that sustainable tourism practices play a crucial role in enhancing community identity with an overall composite mean of 4.40, categorized as “Always”. This shows that the character-first of Bayawanons is deeply rooted in their culture, with a composite mean of 4.45, correlating to “Always”. This implies that participants perceived sustainable tourism as a means of strengthening local identity, promoting inclusivity, and encouraging community participation through cultural events like the Tawo-tawo festival and Charter Anniversary.

Table 3
Relationship between the extent to which the local government and community implement sustainable tourism practices and their perceived impacts on their tourism development

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Zero-Plastic Policy				
Environmental Conservation	0.403	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Economic Growth	0.368	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Community Identity	0.392	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Integration of Sustainable Utility System				
Environmental Conservation	0.393	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Economic Growth	0.337	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Community Identity	0.541	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Cultural Heritage and Preservation				
Environmental Conservation	0.162	0.012	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Economic Growth	0.015	0.820	Failed to	Not
Community Identity	0.270	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant

Level of significance = 0.05

Table 3 presents the relationship between the extent to which the local government and community implement sustainable tourism practices and its perceived impacts on tourism development, and was evaluated using Pearson Correlation Coefficient. The findings reveal the varying degrees of correlation across three sustainable tourism practices: Zero-Plastic Policy, Sustainable Utility Systems, and Cultural Heritage and Preservation, concerning their impacts on environmental conservation, economic growth, and community identity.

The correlation coefficient between Zero-Plastic Policy and environmental conservation is (0.403), economic growth (0.368), and community identity (0.392), all with p-values of

0.000. Since all p-values are less than the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected in each variable. This implies that the zero-plastic policy notably showed a significant relationship on all three indicators of tourism development.

DISCUSSION

The study mainly focused on examining students' extent implementation of sustainable tourism practices in Bayawan City, particularly in zero plastic policy, integration of sustainable utility systems, and cultural heritage and preservation. It also investigated the perceived impacts of these practices on tourism development in the city and explored the correlations between these variables.

Implementation of Zero-Plastic Policy by the LGU and Community

As shown in the table, residents of Bayawan City consistently adhere to established rules of waste collection management for residents. Specifically, this finding shows that the implementation of waste segregation is well communicated to local residents; otherwise, penalties are imposed for noncompliance. In line with this finding, Aragaw (2024) stressed the need for the government to establish effective plastic waste management strategies.

Plastic pollution is a global concern that must be addressed collectively, while innovations should center on the 3Rs: reduce, reuse, and recycle (Kumar et al., 2020). Such initiatives aim to eliminate plastic waste (Shamsuddoha & Kashem, 2024). This policy stimulates a smooth transition to more environmentally friendly materials (Filatov et al., 2018). Thus, it is recommended to increase awareness about the environmental implications of waste (Kalagy et al., 2024), and that zero waste is an ideal aspiration which requires reconfiguration and look at waste not as by product but rather negative externality which has to be consciously addressed (Kumar & Bhati, 2022). This shows that residents consistently adhere to the established waste collection procedures. It likewise goes on to show that the rules set by the local authorities are being followed properly. The implementation of zero-plastic management rules in establishments exhibits a lower mean of 3.51, correlating to "Often". This finding suggests that while these rules are being followed, they are not entirely applied in different establishments within the city and continue to be a challenge, especially in places like wet markets.

In the wet markets, single-use plastic bags are still being used for packaging fresh products such as meat, fish, and seafood due to their nature. This dependency is also justified by the necessity of keeping the freshness intact of these perishable goods and avoiding contamination in as a reference to Mandaue City's Plastic Bag Prohibition Ordinance of 2010 (Sunnexdesk, 2023), mandating the use of eco-friendly packaging bags in business establishments, including restaurants and sari-sari stores, except for wet goods and construction materials. Despite these efforts, plastic used in packaging beverages, fresh meats, fruits, and vegetables remains a current concern (Dey et al., 2020) and is often more prevalent in rural areas than in urban areas (Liu et al., 2021). In light of these findings, Bayawan City proved that proper waste

segregation is possible with discipline and collective community action that even in a small city can bring a spark of change to the community.

Implementation of the Integration of Sustainable Utility System by the LGU and Community

Table 1.2 presents data on the extent to which the local government and community implement the integration of a sustainable utility system in Bayawan City. The findings reveal an overall composite mean of 4.43, interpreted as "Always," indicating that sustainable utility practices are perceived to have been consistently implemented across sectors of the city. This also reflects the strong agreement of the local government and the community in support of environmental policies that are crucial for addressing environmental issues. Among the indicators, the highest-rated item is the utilization of a well-managed sanitary landfill, with a weighted mean of 4.49, also interpreted as "Always." This suggests that the city prioritizes an efficient waste disposal process to minimize environmental damage. With that said, the use of renewable energy sources to reduce carbon footprints garnered a slightly lower weighted mean of 4.27, though it falls within the "Always" category. This underscores the need for implementation improvement.

The city's commendable performance in integrating sustainable utility systems is further recognized as the Best Solid Waste Disposal Facility Award in 2022 by the Environmental Management Bureau of the Department of Environment & Natural Resources Region 7 (Philippine News Agency, 2024). This acknowledgement underscores the city's commitment to sustainable waste management in its core operations. Moreover, Paatlan and Ranga (2024) stressed that providing a more systematic approach between waste and environment are essential in promoting a better environmental integration in urban planning. Similarly, the study of Vaverkova (2019) noted that regular landfill monitoring is required to identify and mitigate risks associated with waste disposal. This data suggest that this system is indeed practiced in collaboration of both the local government and the community.

Implementation of the Cultural Heritage and Preservation by the LGU and Community

The findings reveal that students that the cultural heritage and preservation are often implemented in Bayawan City. One of the highlights is spirit of this festival is still present and highly appreciated by Bayawanons, who are actively involved in preserving this intangible cultural heritage. This festive celebration demonstrates the valuable efforts of the Bayawanons' agricultural community, particularly in rice cultivation, embodying a sense of gratitude for a bountiful harvest. Similarly, educating the local community about the importance of cultural heritage garnered a composite mean of 3.95, correlating to "Often". This means that although it is often perceived that people are becoming increasingly detached from their roots in a rapidly modernized generation, people of Bayawan City continue to educate their community about the value of preserving cultural and traditional practices. In fact, they believed that cultural and traditional practices are

not mere relic of the past but a bridge that connects generations, fostering a strong sense of identity.

Wagner and De Clippele (2023) supported these findings, describing cultural heritage as the embodiment of shared human history, encompassing the tangible artifacts, intangible traditions, languages, rituals, and knowledge passed down through generations. Similarly, Forne and Nguyen (2019) claimed that shared community practices are a mechanism of holding, transferring, and creating knowledge, developed within the frame of community's socio-cultural dynamics. Furthermore, cultural heritage through sustainable tourism practices is vital for maintaining its value and authenticity (Pai et al., 2025). Likewise, Chukwurah et al. (2025) advocated for the development and implementation of comprehensive policies and programs that prioritize the preservation and promotion of local food heritage, while also addressing current challenges. Thus, local government and community's role in safeguarding cultural heritage and traditions is vital in enriching contemporary and future society (Ariwibowo & Fibiona, 2025). Overall, this data shows that cultural heritage and preservation is often implemented by the local government and community.

Perceived Impact of Sustainable Tourism Practices on Tourism Development in Bayawan City in terms of Environmental Conservation

Table 2.1 reveals that the perceived impact of sustainable tourism practices on tourism development in terms of environmental conservation is "Always", with a composite mean of 4.47. This implies that the community greatly supports environmental efforts, particularly in coastal clean-up campaigns, which received a weighted mean of 4.55. This finding aligns with the study of Galluccio and Giambona (2024) who stressed that the economic and social advantages of preserving culture and the environment improved human development outcomes. Similarly, efforts like giving free seedlings to the local farmers and promoting training programs garnered a weighted mean of 4.41, also interpreted as "Always". This signifies that the city is focused on advancing sustainable agriculture initiatives to improve the city's economic growth.

These findings are supported by the Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) through its issuance of Memorandum Circular No. 2023-133 of 2023, mandating all barangays to perform weekly clean-up drives as part of the "Barangay at Kalinisan Day" (BarKaDa) initiative, which seeks to promote cleanliness, sustainability, and active community involvement in barangay levels (DILG, 2023). Bayawan City's participation in these national initiatives, as reflected on the data, highlights its dedication to environmental conservation. The high score for clean-up initiatives shows that community-led environmental efforts are fundamentally integrated into Bayawan's tourism and ecological development plan.

Furthermore, conservation is necessary to achieve sustainable development, and building the capacity of youth, thus having them participate in conservation is imperative for the realization of this effort (Natori et al., 2025). Generally, this data shows the perceived commitment of the Bayawanon people in conserving their natural resources.

Perceived Impact of Sustainable Tourism Practices on Tourism Development in Bayawan City in terms of Economic Growth

Table 2.2 highlights that the perceived impact of sustainable tourism practices on economic growth is “Always,” with the composite mean of 4.28. Survey participants agreed that sustainable tourism is a leading economic development force. Notably, strengthening local businesses through local purchasing and recommendations, with composite mean of 4.47 as “Always”, demonstrates how community support serves as vital economic sustainability element. As noted by Smith et al. (2022), local business promotion works as an economic booster for regional areas.

Additionally, sustainable tourism practices are further reinforced by agricultural investments, with a composite mean of 4.36, along with plantation and diversified crops development with 4.38, as well as agri-farming and aquaculture programs with 4.36, respectively, thus demonstrating the need to integrate agricultural activities into sustainable development models. The rating in "Emerging industries such as Hass Avocado Development," with composite mean of 3.83, interpreted as “Often” indicates that while these industries hold potential, there is a need for further improvement to become primary economic drivers. Supporting this finding, a study by Millan et al. (2023) noted the significance of community’s support to emerging local businesses, which further strengthens local economies.

Consistently, supporting local businesses receives a highest rating, with a composite mean of 4.47. This data reflects an overwhelmingly positive agreement toward community consumption as the leading factor for supporting economic sustainability in Bayawan City. Local product selection over external sources allows money to stay within the community, where it directly strengthens both supply chain networks and new business development. The findings of this table align with the study of Pandey (2025), where tourism development can drive economic growth in destination countries.

Furthermore, the study reveals that sustainable tourism advances the economic development of Bayawan City through local businesses’ support and agricultural plantation projects while simultaneously implementing community development initiatives. Essentially, the data show that economic growth is visible in Bayawan City.

Perceived Impact of Sustainable Tourism Practices on Tourism Development in Bayawan City in terms of Community Identity

Table 2.3 reveals that sustainable tourism practices play a crucial role in enhancing community identity with a composite mean of 4.40, categorized as “Always”. This shows that the character-first of Bayawanons is deeply rooted in their culture, with a composite mean of 4.45, correlating to “Always”. Participants perceived sustainable tourism as a means of strengthening local identity, promoting inclusivity, and encouraging community participation through cultural events like the Tawo-tawo festival and Charter Anniversary. Despite the colonization and exposure to new diverse cultures, languages, and beliefs, these did not detach Filipinos from their roots; instead, they embraced and creatively

adapted external elements of ideas and cultures (Wong, 2021). Undoubtedly, community-based tourism serves as an economic catalyst (Shrestha et al., 2024). It is evident that Bayawanon people strongly preserved their identity while embracing and adapting to modernity.

Relationship between the Extent to which the Local Government and Community Implement Sustainable Tourism Practices and Their Perceived Impacts on their Tourism Development

The findings of this study reveal that sustainable tourism practices play a crucial role in tourism development, particularly in environmental conservation, economic development, and community identity. The correlation coefficient of between Zero-Plastic Policy and environmental conservation is (0.403), economic growth (0.368), and community identity (0.392), all with p-values of 0.000. Since all p-values are less than the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected in each variable. This implies that the zero-plastic policy notably showed a significant relationship on all three indicators of tourism development. These findings are supported by Kumar et al. (2020) who stressed the importance of educating and empowering communities to collectively and responsibly help reduce plastic pollution and make use of alternative options for plastics.

For Integration of Sustainable Utility Systems, significant correlations on all three variables were found: environmental conservation (0.393), economic growth (0.337), and community identity (0.541), all with a p-value of 0.000, thus rejecting the null hypothesis for all variables. These findings suggest that the city's implementation of sustainable utility systems significantly contributes to the community's tourism development without compromising their identity, which garnered the highest correlation value. These findings align with the studies of Tyagi and Anand (2025) and Hayat et al. (2018), who claimed that eco-friendly utilities such as solar energy not only support sustainability but also strengthen communal resilience and innovation in agriculture and waste management like water treatment and irrigation.

On the other hand, Cultural Heritage and Preservation showed a more varied results. Notably, of the three variables, economic growth revealed no significant relationship with p-value of (0.015), while environmental conservation (0.162) and community identity (0.270) revealed a significant positive relationship respectively. These findings indicate that while cultural preservation efforts enhance environmental awareness and strengthen Bayawanons' identity, they do not directly impact Bayawan's economic growth. As Keitsch (2020) pointed out, economic growth does not inevitably promote heritage conservation

Overall, the study reveals that not all sustainable tourism practices equally impact all aspects of tourism development. While practices like the Zero-Plastic Policy and Sustainable Utility Systems show significant positive relationships with economic growth, environmental conservation, and community identity, Cultural Heritage and Preservation show no significant correlation with economic growth.

Conclusions

The data gathered revealed the active implementation of sustainable tourism practices, including zero plastic policy; integration of sustainable utility system; and cultural heritage and preservation. The data reported the extent of implementation shows a significant relationship. The outcomes of embracing these sustainable practices leads to enhanced environmental quality and a strong sense of identity creating a place where both the environment and culture are valued and protected. The perceived impact of sustainable tourism practices on tourism development in Bayawan City in terms of the following aspects, environmental conservation, economic growth, and community identity, has a significant relationship based on the data gathered on environmental conservation and on community identity. In contrast, the data on economic growth showed that there is no significant relationship between the perceived impacts of sustainable tourism practices on cultural heritage and preservation. This suggests the need for more strategic, culturally sensitive economic integration. Nonetheless, the findings of this study emphasize the importance of continuing investment in eco-friendly facilities, involving the community, and strict enforcement of rules and policies for overall tourism development while protecting the environment and culture.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the researcher offers the following recommendations to the local government and tourism officials, local community, and tourists:

Local Government and Tourism Officials:

1. Enforce strong policies that promote eco-friendly practices in tourism, such as waste reduction, water conservation, and renewable energy in accommodation and tour operations.
2. Encourage other cities to embrace agricultural marketing initiatives like supporting local farmers through the Department of Agriculture and marketing their products directly to the city. This allows farmers to capture a large share and gain control over the pricing strategies. This led to enhancing farmer livelihoods and urban food access.
3. Launch more agricultural sectors like hass- avocado to help the economic growth in the City.

Local Community:

4. Actively participate in the planning and decision-making processes related to tourism development and strengthen the growth of community-based tourism initiatives.
5. Invest in skill-building programs to be able to take on higher-paying, sustainable jobs in the tourism sector.

Tourists:

6. Experience the unique and authentic spirit Bayawan City and enjoy some of its local products. "Bring home the authenticity of Bayawan. Buy Local."

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study upholds ethical standards, emphasizing honesty, respect, and protection of participants' rights. Participants are asked for informed consent, stating the study's aim, voluntary participation, and data handling. Confidentiality and data privacy are maintained to protect respondents' identities and cultural sensitivities, considering the study's potential impact on the local community's well-being and heritage. Furthermore, the findings of the study would be disseminated responsibly and transparently to benefit local policymaking and community planning.

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